

Enhancing the Stability of ResBased Microgrids by Using ANFIS Controllers with Back To Back Converters

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ABSTRACT: This research explores a smart grid based on an innovative control method called adaptive-neuro fuzzy interfaced system (ANFIS) to address power quality challenges. The utility-grid is connected to a full-scale wind turbine that uses permanent magnet synchronous generators using back-to-back voltage-source converters, or BtB VSCs. The front-to-back converters' dc-link capacitors are hardwired into PV solar generators. Maximising system efficiency is achieved without the need for dc/dc conversion steps. To optimise the use of renewable energy sources, the suggested architecture has separate maximum power point tracking for the wind and PV producers. The VSCs are regulated using the rotating reference frame's vector control technique. To examine the overall stability, we build comprehensive small signal models for each component of the system. The results of the simulations for various smart grid modes and non-linear fault conditions demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed control technique.

KEYWORDS: adaptive-neurofuzzyinterfacedsystem(ANFIS),wind,solar,VSC.

I.INTRODUCTION:Wind and solar power generating costs have been decreasing at a remarkable pace during the last decade. With the help of financial and technological incentives, the worldwide capacity of wind turbines and photovoltaic (PV) panels has increased from 6 GW in 2006 to 487 GW in 2016, respectively [1]. The generating units are formed because power-electronic converters are used as an interface to the load side or the utility grid, which is necessary since wind and solar energy is intermittent and uncontrolled [2]-[3]. Solar power, as shown in [4]-[5] or wind power, as seen in [6]-[8], is the most common kind of distributed generating system in the literature. There has been some discussion about combining nearby solar and wind power in order to get the most out of the renewable energy sources [9]- [22]. Here are some things to know about wind and solar power cogeneration: 1) The two sources of energy are often complimentary, thus using them together improves operational efficiency [23]. 2) Wind and solar co-generators work together to maximise land resource utilisation, which in turn improves capital investment [24]. Thirdly, the utility-grid may be more

dynamically supported by wind-solar cogeneration systems than by static PV generators because of the wind generators' mechanical system's possible moment of inertia [8]. Increased generating dependability is one benefit of having two energy sources [9]– [10]. There has been little discussion of grid-connected wind-PV cogeneration systems [9]-[15]. However, for independent off-grid use, there are a number of wind-PV cogeneration systems that have been suggested [10], [16]-[22]. An independent wind-photovoltaic cogeneration system is suggested in references [16]–[17]. A laboratory-scale system is shown in [19]-[20], while a small-scale system including a single-phase cogeneration has been suggested in [18]. The system architecture in [16]-[20] often includes a shared dc-bus that connects many renewable energy resources that are interfaced with converters in parallel, which might lead to a decrease in overall system efficiency and an increase in cost [12]. To prevent instabilities that can result from the dynamics of the generated contacts, which might occur when power converters are cascaded, strict controller coordination is essential [25]-[26]. The PV generator and energy storage unit interfaced with the dc-dc converter are described in [21] using a back-to-back (BtB) voltage-source converter (VSC) linked to a doubly-fed induction generator. A PV generator that charges a bank of batteries and is connected to a wind-driven induction generator via a VSC is suggested in [22].

Highlighting the effective integration of renewable energy resources with low use of power-electronic conversion steps, the wind-PV cogeneration systems in [21]- [22] are described. But these solutions are only meant for certain off-grid uses. Using multiple-input converters has enhanced the utility-grid integration of renewable energy resources [12]-[14]. In [12], the authors suggest a dc-dc converter that is fused: buck/buck-boost. In [13] and [14], the authors suggest a connected transformer and a dc-dc converter with a

current-source interface, respectively. On the other hand, ac-dominated power systems may not benefit from the suggested solutions in [12]-[14] since they rely on dc power distribution. So far as the authors are aware, only [15] has dealt with the topic of grid-connected wind-PV systems in tandem. The BtB VSCs are an integral part of the system described in [15] that connects the utility-grid to the PV and wind producers. An outer loop proportional-and-integral (PI) dc voltage controller adjusts the dc-link voltage on the machine-side VSC so that it matches the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) value of the PV panels. The synchronous detection technique is used to derive the reference values of the machine-side currents, and a hysteresis current controller is used for regulation. In order to inject the total currents into the utility-grid, the grid-side VSC uses a hysteresis grid-current controller. Despite the system's potential advantages, the following issues have been identified: 1) operating both VSCs is required for MPPT of either PV or wind power, which in certain cases may be a hassle

causes the system's dependability to decline and losses to rise. One example is when the wind speed is too low to generate any power from the wind turbine; in this case, the machine-side VSC may not be able to follow the solar PV MPPT dc-link voltage [15]. 2) Hysteresis controllers are used to manage the machine and grid-side converter currents, which leads to a variable switching frequency and greater harmonic contents. Inspired by the potential advantages of wind-photovoltaic (PV) production systems, this study presents a novel architecture that is both easy to implement and very effective in connecting PV and wind generators to the utility grid. The following are some of the paper's contributions: 1) The installation of BtB VSCs, which eliminate the need for additional dc/dc conversion stages, in a grid-connected wind-PV cogeneration system. 2) Separate MPPT operation, in which the wind generator's and PV system's voltage-source

rectifiers (VSRs) and voltage-source inverters (VSIs) are used exclusively to accomplish maximum power point tracking (MPPT). (3) To characterise the overall stability of the wind-PV cogeneration system, a full small-signal state-space model has to be developed. 4) Various operational situations, including utility grid failures, were used to examine the performance of the proposed system using time-domain simulations.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY:

The authors S. B. Kjaer, Z. Chen, and F. Blaabjerg are suggested to Power capacity, efficient production, delivery, and utilisation are under increasing demand as the world's electrical energy consumption continues to rise. Worldwide, conventional electricity grids are undergoing a transformation, a Wind turbines, photovoltaic (PV) generators, fuel cells, small hydro, wave generators, and gas/steam powered combined heat and power stations are among the renewable and nonrenewable energy sources that are being integrated into power systems at the distribution level through a large number of dispersed generation (DG) units. Integrating scattered generating units for high performance and efficiency in power systems relies heavily on power electronics, a field concerned with the efficient processing of electric power. In this article, we take a look at how power electronics have been used to integrate DG units, namely wind power, fuel cells, and PV generators. A. Yazdani and P. P. Dash have suggested a method of controlling a distribution-connected, single-stage, three-phase photovoltaic (PV) system. One DC-link voltage regulator and one current-control loop form the basis of the control. Using the current-control method, the dynamics of the PV system are isolated from the loads and the network. The actual power output may be controlled and maximised with the help of the DC-link voltage-control

method. To ensure that the current-control loop's dynamics remain autonomous from the rest of the system, it is recommended that it do the appropriate feedforward actions. In order to make the dynamics of the PV system resistant to the nonlinear feature of the PV array, a feed forward compensation technique is suggested for the DC-link voltage-control loop. As a result, PV system controllers may be optimised for a variety of operating circumstances via design. We also do a modal/sensitivity analysis on a linearized determine the nature of the interactions between the PV system and the network/loads, assess the controllers' resilience, characterise the system's dynamic features, and model the total system. The suggested control approach ensures that the PV system's dynamics are separate from the distribution network's, according to the modal analysis findings. As a consequence, the PV system will not cause distribution network instability. Additionally, it is shown that the dynamics of the network do not impact the stability and dynamic characteristics of the PV system. This means that the PV system keeps its stability and dynamic qualities even when the line length, line X/R ratio, load type, and distance from the PV system undergo significant alterations.

III. PROPOSED

SYSTEM CONFIGURATION:

- IV. Figure 1 shows the components of the proposed system, which include a VSR for wind generator interface and a VSI for utility-grid connection of the cogeneration system. A dc wire is used to connect the PV generator directly to the dc-link capacitor of the BtB VSCs [27]. A diode and an insulated-gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) form each of the six cells that make up the VSR and VSI, two-level converters. The next parts provide the full control and modelling of the suggested system.
- #### A. A Wind Turbine

V. Due to its low operating cost and minimal maintenance requirements, a full-scale wind turbine (FSWT) with a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) is chosen [2]. The model of the wind turbine looks like this:

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} C_p(\beta, \lambda) \rho \pi R^2 v_{wind}^3$$

$$\lambda = \frac{R \omega_r}{v_{wind}} \quad (1)$$

where P_m is the mechanical power captured by the wind turbine blades; C_p is the rotor coefficient which is a non-linear function of the blade pitch angle (β) and the tip-speed ratio (λ); ρ is the air density; R is the radius of the wind turbine blade; v_{wind} is the wind speed; and ω_r is the mechanical speed of the rotor. In this paper, β is set to zero in the normal operating conditions to maximize the wind power generation [13].

A. Machine-Side Voltage Source Rectifier (VSR)

The VSR is utilized to capture the maximum wind power by regulating the

$$I_{sq}^* = (\omega_r^* - \omega_r) G_s(s), \quad I_{sd}^* = 0$$

The PI speed controller ($G_s(s) = g_{ps} + g_{is}/s$) is implemented in the outer loop, where s represents the differential operator and the superscript “*” denotes the reference values of the variable. The speed controller regulates the PMSG speed to the optimal value (ω_r^*) and dictates the q -component of stator current reference (I_{sq}^*), whereas I_{sd}^* is set to zero to operate at maximum produced torque [19].

$$I_{sq}^* = (\omega_r^* - \omega_r) G_s(s),$$

$$I_{sd}^* = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where s represents the differential operator. Solving (3) and (4), assuming $I_{AN} \approx I_{AN}^*$ within the bandwidth of ($G_i(s) = g_{pi} + g_{ii}/s$)

The PMSG is modeled as following,

$$\vec{v}_s = R_s \vec{i}_s + L_s \frac{d\vec{i}_s}{dt} + j P \omega_r (\psi + L_s \vec{i}_s) \quad (2)$$

$$J \frac{d}{dt} \omega_r + \beta \omega_r = \frac{3}{2} P \psi I_{sq} - T_m \quad (3)$$

In (2), v and i are the stator voltage and current in the complex vectors representation, respectively, where a complex vector such

that X_d and X_q are the direct (d -) and quadrature (q -) components of X in the rotating reference frame; R_A and L_A are the stator inducting resistance and inductance, respectively; j is the imaginary unit number;

ψ is the flux linkage of the rotor magnets; P is the number of poles pairs; T_m is the mechanical torque; whereas J and β are the motor inertia, and viscous friction, respectively.

mechanical rotor speed of the PMSG to follow the MPPT characteristics in Fig. 2, using the PI speed controller ($G_s(s)$) in (4).

the speed controller ($G_A(s)$), and setting $g_{2A}/g_{1A} = \beta/J$, the closed-loop transfer function of the speed controller

beco

mes;

$$\omega_r / \omega_r^* = \left(\frac{3}{2} P \psi g_{ps} / J \right) / \left(s + \left(\frac{3}{2} P \psi g_{ps} / J \right) \right),$$

where the

$$\frac{3}{2} P \psi g_{ps} / J \quad [\text{rad/s}],$$

Bandwidth is $\frac{3}{2} P \psi g_{ps} / J$ and is selected to be around 10% of the bandwidth of the inner current controller [discussed in the following paragraph]. The speed controller parameters, i.e., g_{1A} and

g_{2A} , can be tuned accordingly. As shown

in Fig. 1 and (5), a PI current controller

isemplot so that the generated stator currents of thePMSG follow the corresponding referencesin(4).

$$\bar{v}_s = (\bar{i}_s^* - \bar{i}_s)G_i(s) + jP\omega_r^\circ L_s \bar{i}_s +$$

Where isthedecouplingloops; Hisagain;whereasthesuperscript“°”denote the steady-state value of the variable.The current controller in (5) is designed by solving (2) and (5). By setting

Fig. 1. The proposed wind-PV cogeneration system.

Fig.2.Mechanicalcharacteristicsofthewindturbinatdifferentwind speeds.

Lates the PMSG speed to the optimal value(ω_r^*) and dictates the q- component of statorcurrent reference (I_{sq}^*), whereas I_{sd}^* is set tozero to operate at maximum produced torque[19].

the closed looptransferfunctionofthecurrentcontroller

becomes;

where the bandwidth of the current controlleris $1/\tau_i = g_{pi}/L_s$ [rad/s],

and is selected to be about 10-20% of theswitching frequency of the VSR. Fig. 1.

Theproposedwind-PVcogenerationssystem.Levels.

$$I_{sd}/I_{sd}^* = 1/(\tau_i s + 1),$$

$$g_{ii}/g_{pi} = R_s/L_s.$$

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS:

1.1 Proposed simlink diagram

Fig.4.2 The step response of the dc-link voltage to verify the developed small signal model

Windsolar references:

Fig.4.3 Wind and solar both:

Fig.4.4Wind only

Fig.4.5Solar only

Fig4.63 phaseground

VII. CONCLUSION:

This research explores a smart grid that is efficient and based on ANFIS regulation in order to improve electricity quality. It is the job of the VSR on the wind generator side to maximise wind power extraction in response to changes in wind speed. The VSI's responsibilities on the utility-grid side include getting the most power out of the PV generator, balancing the input and output powers across the dc-link capacitor, and keeping the PCC voltage constant in all modes of operation. The suggested ANFIS control-based method improves power quality while decreasing the network's failure tolerance.

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